

QUALITY STATUS OF EXISTING SERVICES OF HIGHER EDUCATION: A STUDY ON SELECTED GOVT. COLLEGES OF NORTHERN BANGLADESH

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Abstract- The right to education is the right not only to access education but also to receive quality education. Quality Services need to be assured in every level of educational institutions. It is very much needed for higher education as it supplies bottom to top most levels human capital to labor markets. Govt. colleges of Bangladesh affiliated to National University play a gearing role to increase the rate of higher education. Bangladesh education sector is realizing the extensive impact trying to ensure customer services with its tangible and intangible dimensions to increase the quality of education. Especially quality education of Bangladesh, is facing enormous challenges regarding quality of services provided by the institutions. Stakeholders (students and related others) do not get due quality services from the educational institutions. It is truer for higher education institutions like the government colleges. The study is trying to explore the present scenarios of services and their quality status by interviewing 80 (20 from each four selected government colleges of northern Bangladesh) teachers, staffs and service personnel through descriptive statistics by a structured questionnaire and a checklist. The study concludes to provide real scenarios about present status of services in government colleges. The study finds that among fourteen service dimensions most are average and below average and few service dimensions are in good status.

Keywords: Service Quality, Higher Education, Government Colleges.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is a birth right and fundamental need of human being. Quality is the heart of education. It influences what students learn and what benefits they draw from their education. It has been realized that quality of education prepares one for all pursuits of life and the absence of an acceptable level of quality education becomes mere formalism devoid of any purpose or substance. Service quality is an integral part of quality education. It needs to be assured in every level of educational institutions.[¹]

Quality is a vital part of higher education (HE). To ensure quality education government colleges should provide quality services to the students. Most of the time, the affiliation university named National University (NU) of Bangladesh is

busy with enrolment of students, publishing results, awarding certificates and many more beside those. But there is hardly any activity of the NU to ensure quality education and to develop of tangibles (infrastructural) and intangibles (non-infrastructural) services and facilities in the govt. colleges.[²]

A national strategy plan recently developed by Bangladesh government which highlights that limited access in HE; weak governance and management of institutions, and low quality of HE are the major issues that need to be addressed. Government is also trying to accomplish the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030. The fourth goal of SDGs is to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and to promote lifelong opportunities for all.[³]

Students are interested in quality education with better services, adequate academic environment, employability skills, active participation, etc. It is up to the higher education institution to satisfy those needs with the infrastructure and the services it provides to students.[4] Therefore, it is vital for educational institutions to actively monitor the quality of services and commit to continuous improvement to the needs of stakeholders.[5]

Service facilities or items or parameters are significant for providing quality HE. Every HE institution is built to serve the tertiary education, with physical assets and non-physical facilities. Physical assets and facilities give educational institutions their complete shape and teaching learning environment.[6] Various critical impacts of facilities on the activities of an HE institution is considered to attract students and researchers to provide environment for faster knowledge creation and its impact on students' perceptions, their pedagogic knowledge and experience. Government of Bangladesh allocates budgets for govt. educational institutions of which major portion is used for teachers' and staffs' salaries and remunerations and very small portion for the development of physical and non-physical services. The maintenance of quality and standards of physical assets and facilities is very challenging.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A number of studies have been conducted on HE and service quality in different areas of the world. The studies have agreed that the education quality can be determined by multiple dimensions that help the HE institutions to design appropriate value propositions, but which factors influence the students' perceptions about these dimensions are needed to give attention in case of government colleges as a sub sector of HE in Bangladesh. This study investigates exploring services and their quality in govt. colleges and finds out the opinion from colleges' teachers, staffs and service personnel about quality or

status of service facilities. A close ended structured questionnaire as well as a checklist has been used for primary data collection to explore the status of the services of the selected HE govt. colleges. Govt. colleges' teachers, staffs and service personnel are the service providers who deals with service dimensions and best knows about services in a college. So, they have been selected as respondents of this study. Though it is a descriptive survey, a close observation has been done during the data collection period. A number of books, thesis, periodicals and newspapers, college note books, college magazines, has been consulted for secondary data to explore service quality status about govt. colleges' and service facilities. Here, the data regarding the services for HE of NU affiliated government colleges have been identified and tried to find out status service quality.

Md. Bayezid Hossain (2017) examined to identify present scenario and policies, to ensure quality in higher education, and to improve the institutional academic infrastructure by accessing to knowledge and information by integrating ICT and laboratory technologies into learning, and modernizing student learning spaces and support facilities.[7] Alrafa Akter (2017) showed some of the facilities i.e., experienced faculty, high speed net, research support, well equipped class room, update course, rich online library, motivation for research, faculty exchange, work load for teachers, credit transfer, latest learning, and training for new teachers that are being provided, improve the quality of higher education.[8] Vairaiyan et al.(2016) aimed to develop empirically a hierarchical model for measuring service quality in higher education.⁹ Husain Salilul Akareem & Syed Shahadat Hossain (2016) found that status of students for scholarship, extracurricular activities, parents' education, age, previous result has a significant influence on perception about quality of higher education.[10] Tejinder Sharma (2014) run a study on perceptions of service quality and identify the gap between their expectations and these perceptions by using the modified

service quality (SERVQUAL) instrument to measure five constructs: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.^[11] Therefore, from the different studies we can summarize that the status of services has a great impact on quality of higher education.

The objective of this paper is to explore the existing services and their status or quality of HE in govt. colleges of northern Bangladesh. Whether the quality of services are feasible, available and accessible or not.

3. JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

The importance of higher education is increasing day by day. The demand of seats to enroll in HE government colleges is increasing. But the service facilities and their quality are not increasing in that proportion. NU is busy with enrolment of students, publishing results, awarding certificates and many more beside those. But there is hardly any activity of the NU to ensure quality education and to develop of tangibles (infrastructural) and intangibles (non-infrastructural) facilities in the govt. colleges.^[12] Therefore, quality of services in government colleges is not so update for the fulfillment of requirement of HE. This study will attempt to address the closely related issues of service quality in higher education in government colleges. Through conducting the study, an overall scenario of service quality in government colleges will be drawn. This study might be helpful to develop the knowledge sector of service strategies and to improve the service quality system of HE in the government colleges.

4. METHODOLOGY

This is a descriptive survey designed to collect data from teachers and staffs opinions to explore the status or quality of services in HE from selected govt. colleges. Teachers and staffs has been selected as respondents in this study because they are the service provider falling different problems during providing services and well known about a service facility and

its availability, accessibility and status. Four govt. colleges have been selected systemetically from the northern division Rajshahi and Rangpur of Bangladesh. Rajshahi Colleges (RC) and Rajshahi Govt. Women College (RGWC) from Rajshahi Division, and Carmichael College Rangpur (CCR) and Dinajpur Govt. College (DGC) from Rangpur Division has been selected from top ten ranking from all divisions of Bangladesh by NU, 2016. A questionnaire (Annexure-I) to explore status of services and a check list (Annexure-II) to find out general information about selected govt. colleges have been used to collect data from the respondents by a four points Likert type scale about the status of different services of selected colleges. The methods have followed here to have availability of a service facility indicating “Yes” or “No” and to measure the status of a service facility comparatively denotes any of the degree by “Very good=4” or “Good=3” or “Average=2” or “Below Average=1” for the degree of feasibility, availability, accessibility and quality of the service items/parameters. After that, the surveyed data has been modified by simple MS excel 2013 program to calculate respondents’ mean opinions and standard deviations about service facilities. If the score of mean opinion of respondents is greater than or equal to 3.75 the service status indicate “very good”; if mean score ≥ 2.75 to < 3.75 the service status is “good”; or if mean score ≥ 1.75 to < 2.75 , the service status is “average” or if mean score < 1.75 , the service status is below average”. A deviation of 0.25 has been taken to find out nearest status. The service status has been identified for each college separately. Then the aggregated mean has been averaged for each college and also each service aspect separately and combined. A sample survey of 80 teachers (principals, professors, associate professors, assistant professors, lecturers) and staffs (head assistant, other service personnel) has been conducted (20 from in each of the selected colleges) to find out the real service facilities and their degree of quality to fit in HE. The service facilities investigated here include teaching learning services (10 parameters), ICT

services(3 parameters), administrative services(3parameters), class rooms and college environment(6 parameters), co-curricular and extra-curricular activities(4 parameters), accommodation facilities(6 parameters), recreation facilities(7 parameters), facilities for publication(2 parameters), transportation services(3 parameters), library services(3 parameters), laboratories services(2 parameters), creation of job opportunity(2 parameters), awards and recognition for academic achievements(3 parameters), and other facilities to students, teachers and staffs(6 parameters).

ancient college but its area of land is less than that of CCR and DGC but more than that of RGWC. There are 98 students per teacher in RC, 70 students in RGWC, 130 students DGC, and 120 students in CCR, whereas, public universities of our country have 24 to 30 students per teacher. The authorities of these colleges argued that they have to face a lot of problems to give quality service to the vast number of students with limited number of teachers and workforce. It is found that about 310 students are enrolled in a subject like management in DGC but there are only 40 sets of traditional benches where 120 students at best can seat at a time during a class period. Hostel seat capacity is very limited in almost all govt. colleges in Bangladesh. In RC has only 838 boarding seats for 23,549 male and female students. Most of the hostel buildings are aged and old pattern. There is very limited opportunity of modern dowering system. The other services or facilities i.e., no. of teachers (acting), no. of regular employees, no. of honours and master's subjects, multimedia class rooms are very limited.

5. GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT SELECTED GOVT. COLLEGES

It is observed from table-1 that the government colleges are varied from each other in terms of their establishment and area of land available, number of academic buildings, accommodation capacity, transportation and other infrastructural facilities. Among those colleges, RC is most

TABLE-1: GENERAL DATA ABOUT SELECTED GOVT. COLLEGES

Sl. No.	Items	RC	RGWC	CCR	DGC
1.	Year of Establishment (A.D.)	1873	1962	1916	1942
2.	Area of Land (acres)	35	10.62	206.33	66
3.	No. of hostels with boarding capacity	4 (838) (1) Muslim Hostel (10 Buildings) (2) Hindu Hostel (3) Women's Hostel-1 (4) Women's Hostel-2	1(360) (2 Buildings)	4+3 (1000) (7 buildings) Male hostels had been closed for clash of students seats during survey	3+3 (727) (6 Buildings)
4.	No. of teachers (acting)	239 (Prof. 36, Associate Prof. 52, Assist .Prof. 91, Lecturers 60)	72 (Prof. 7, Associate Prof. 16, Assist. Prof. 19, Lecturers 30)	168 (Prof. 18, Associate Prof. 43, Assistant Prof. 61, Lecturers 46)	111 (Prof. 10, Associate Prof. 27, Assist. Prof. 42, Lecturers 35)
5.	No. of regular employees	35	14	29	19
6.	No. of employees master roll	76	33	108	125
7.	No. of students studying (during survey)	23549	4400	19890	15286
8.	No. of seats enrollment in Honours First Year	3850	1140	3335	3195
9.	No. of seats enrollment in Master's	6000	300	5000	3000
10.	Degrees awarded	HSC; BA, BSS, BSc, BBA (pass); BA, BSS, BSc, BBA (Hons); MA, MSS, MSc, MBA.	HSC; BA, BSS, BSc, (pass); BA, BSS, BSc, (Hons); MA, MSS, MSc.	HSC; BA, BSS, BSc, BBA (pass); BA, BSS, BSc, BBA (Hons); MA, MSS, MSc, MBA	HSC; BA, BSS, BSc, BBA (pass); BA, BSS, BSc, BBA (Hons); MA, MSS, MSc, MBA
11.	No. of Honours Subjects	22(Arts-6, SS-4, Science-8, Business-4)	14(Arts-5, SS-2, Science-7)	18 (Arts-6, SS-3, Science-5, Business-4)	15 (Arts-5, SS-3, Science-5, Business-2)
12.	No. of Maters Subjects	22(Arts-6, SS-4, Science-8, Business-4)	5 (Arts-3, SS-2)	16 (Arts-6, SS-3, Science-5, Business-2)	15 (Arts-5, SS-3, Science-5, Business-2)
13.	Affiliated University	All The selected colleges are affiliated to National University (NU) of Bangladesh.			
14.	No. of General (traditional) Class rooms	2	16	18	30
15.	No. of Multimedia Class rooms	74	8	36	17

16.	Capacity to seat for exam	4000	1850	3300	3000
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Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Descriptive Statistics with cross tabulation has been done to determine the status or quality of services in selected govt. colleges for each parameter the respondents' opinion are numerically expressed. Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) has been measured and calculated college and parameter wise from given opinion of respondents through MS Excel 2013 then calculated Means are aggregated and averaged to find out actual status of services of selected govt, colleges and made comments.

6.1 Teaching-learning Services

Table-2 shows that the aggregate mean scores is 2.60 and of the teaching-learning services in selected govt. colleges.

TABLE-2: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT TEACHING-LEARNING SERVICES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Name of respondents college	Respondents' opinions mean					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
1. Traditional teaching tools/materials: blackboards and chalks, board cleaners/dusters, moving boards etc.	3.35	2.80	2.75	2.25	2.78	0.76
2. Modern tools and materials: white board and markers, Multimedia Projectors, Sound systems, project pointer, cordless speakers, laptops, pen drives etc.	3.50	2.80	2.50	3.00	2.95	0.74
3. Class room Physical Environment: Chair bench decoration and Lighting	3.55	2.90	2.50	2.75	2.93	0.76
4. Class time/schedule and with sufficient class durations	3.40	3.20	3.25	2.50	3.09	0.73
5. Lesson Plan (lectures time, feedback time, test time, FAQ for students) and Course Plan	3.35	2.30	2.50	1.50	2.41	0.92
6. Team works for solving study problems	2.80	1.70	1.75	2.00	2.06	0.75
7. Individual Assignment/group assignments	2.90	2.00	2.00	1.50	2.1	0.87
8. Course Evaluation (in course/annual test)	2.75	2.70	3.00	3.00	2.86	0.82
9. Attendances, appearing in the class tests	3.20	2.80	2.50	3.00	2.88	0.74
10. Individual and group Presentations of Term Papers, Seminar Papers	2.65	1.10	1.75	2.00	1.88	0.89
Aggregate Mean	3.15	2.43	2.45	2.35	2.60	
Comments/Remarks	Average (Mean)\geq1.75 to $<$2.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

6.2 ICT services

Table-3 shows that the aggregate mean scores is 2.75 on ICT services in selected HE govt. colleges. The ICT services about computer labs, skill development of students,

and broad band facilities are with the aggregate mean scores of 3.12, 2.73, 2.75, and 2.42 for RC, RGWC, CCR and DGC respectively. The Respondents shows overall good remarks about ICT services of government colleges.

TABLE-3: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT ICT SERVICES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' mean opinions					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
11. Computer lab with using facilities	3.20	2.10	3.00	2.50	2.70	0.50
12. ICT skill development short courses (MS-Office, internet browsing, email sending, download and upload of files and text etc.)	3.15	2.90	2.75	2.25	2.76	0.38
13. Broad band/wifi internet using facilities	3.00	3.20	2.50	2.50	2.80	0.24
Aggregate Mean	3.12	2.73	2.75	2.42	2.75	
Comments/Remarks	Good (mean>=2.75 to <3.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

6.3 Administrative services

Table-4 shows that the aggregate mean scores on the Administrative services is 2.12 in selected HE govt. colleges about availability of service personnel, cashiers and key informant officers. Respondents show the average opinion about administrative services. The RC shows a high mean score

of 2.82 which is criterion of good remarks mean scores whereas, the DGC shows a below average mean scores of 1.67. We also found that in case of sufficient cashiers parameter/item, the respondents have shown the lowest aggregate mean scores of 1.96 with a SD of 0.85.

TABLE-4: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT ADMINISTRATIVE SERVICES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' mean opinions					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
14. Sufficient employees for different services	3.05	2.10	2.25	2.00	2.35	0.75
15. Is there Sufficient Cashiers	2.60	2.00	2.00	1.25	1.96	0.85
16. is there sufficient key information officers	2.80	1.90	1.75	1.75	2.05	0.79
Aggregate Mean	2.82	2.00	2.00	1.67	2.12	
Comments/Remarks	Average (Mean>=1.75 to <2.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19.

6.4 Class room and college environment

Table-5 shows the aggregate mean scores of 2.39 on class room facilities and college environment in selected HE govt. colleges about comfortable desks, accessibility of toilets and washrooms, group work facilities, decoration of outdoor seats and tents, attractive natural environment. Respondents have shown the highest aggregate mean scores of 2.85 with SD 0.84 on the item 'college trees' gardens and flowers' gardens are well decorated and neat and clean.' The RC shows higher score of 3.44 whereas CCR shows lower scores of 1.83.

TABLE-5: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT CLASS ROOMS AND COLLEGE ENVIRONMENT FACILITIES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' mean opinions					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
17. Well-equipped and comfortable desks for note taking in the class rooms	3.00	2.10	2.25	2.25	2.40	0.87
18. Easy accessible toilets and washrooms for both gender and disabled-abled students	3.75	1.90	1.50	2.00	2.29	1.05
19. Comfortable Desk arrangement for group work and group discussions	3.15	1.80	1.25	2.00	2.05	0.99
20. Well decorated outdoor seats and tents for group discussions	3.25	1.60	1.25	1.75	1.96	0.97
21. College Buildings and infrastructures are well decorated	3.75	2.20	2.50	2.75	2.80	0.86
22. College tress gardens and flower gardens are well decorated and neat and clean	3.75	2.40	2.25	3.00	2.85	0.84
Aggregate Mean	3.44	2.00	1.83	2.29	2.39	
Comments/Remarks	Average (Mean) \geq 1.75 to $<$ 2.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19.

6.5 Co-curricular and Extracurricular Activities

Table-6 shows that the aggregate mean scores on co-curricular and extracurricular activities in selected HE govt. colleges about BNCC and rover scout, multi-functional clubs, co-curricular and extracurricular activities, and different types

of fairs is 2.64. Respondents have shown the highest mean scores of 3.00 with SD 0.76 about the item 'Sufficient BNCC and rover scout volunteers from different sessions and departments.' The RC shows higher scores of 3.64 and RGWC shows lower scores of 1.93.

TABLE-6: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT CO-CURRICULAR AND EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' mean opinions					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
23. Sufficient BNCC and rover scout volunteers from different sessions and departments	3.60	2.40	3.00	3.00	3.00	0.76
24. Multi-functional clubs to enhance students' personal development and creativity	3.75	1.90	2.75	2.25	2.66	0.98
25. Facilities in different co-curricular and extracurricular activities	3.65	2.20	2.50	2.50	2.71	0.80
26. Arrangement of different types of fairs (Science fairs, Olympiads etc.)	3.55	1.20	1.75	2.25	2.19	1.04
Aggregate Mean	3.64	1.93	2.50	2.50	2.64	
Comments/Remarks	Average (Mean) \geq 1.75 to $<$ 2.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

6.6 Accommodation Facilities

Table-7 shows that the aggregate mean scores on accommodation facilities in selected HE govt. colleges is 2.30. That shows the average remarks of respondents. Most of the colleges have not sufficient hostels facilities. The ratio relating

seats with students is very high and the environment of hostels and quality of bedding and meals are not good. Even sometimes the hostels are gone to under lock due to unusual political power of ruling parties. Though the respondents show average remarks, in some cases it goes below average.

TABLE-7: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT ACCOMMODATION FACILITIES

	Respondents' opinions mean	

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	SD
27. In hostel accommodation with neat and clean environment	2.25	2.10	2.50	2.25	2.28	0.80
28. Outside hostel accommodation, Good mess, hostels etc. nearer to college	2.40	2.70	2.25	2.50	2.46	0.65
29. Comfortable beddings in hostel seats boarding facilities	2.10	2.00	2.25	2.00	2.09	0.70
30. Indoor and outdoor game and sports and football and cricket tournaments in hostels	2.80	2.00	2.25	2.50	2.39	0.83
31. Well decorated Guest room to meet students with guardians	1.95	2.00	2.50	1.75	2.05	0.73
32. Common rooms for ladies and gents	2.80	2.40	3.00	2.00	2.55	0.83
Aggregate Mean	2.38	2.20	2.46	2.17	2.30	
Comments/Remarks	Average (Mean)\geq1.75 to $<$2.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

6.7 Recreation Facilities

Table-8 shows the aggregate mean scores on recreation facilities in selected HE govt. colleges is 2.75. That shows 'good' remarks of respondents about different aspects of religious institutions, gymnasiums, games and sports facilities, excursions, TV with satellite connections. The RC and CCR

have good remarks on recreation facilities whereas RGWC and DGC have average remarks. The RGWC and DGC have no central gymnasium with tools and equipment with a skilled physician as the respondents have shown 'No' opinion in that case.

TABLE-8: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT RECREATION FACILITIES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' opinions mean					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
33. Central auditorium for arranging meetings, occasions, seminar and symposiums etc.	3.35	1.80	2.75	3.25	2.79	0.90
34. Central religious institutions for prayer	3.35	2.30	3.50	3.50	3.16	0.80
35. Central gymnasium with tools and equipment with a skilled physician	2.55	0.00	1.25	0.00	0.95	1.14
36. Games and Sports tournaments with different years	3.15	2.50	2.75	2.75	2.79	0.67
37. Arrangement of national days and cultural functions	3.55	3.40	3.75	3.50	3.55	0.55
38. Study tours/Excursion every year	3.25	3.30	3.50	3.50	3.39	0.63
39. Hostels TV rooms with satellite channel connections	2.80	3.00	2.50	2.25	2.64	0.77
Aggregate Mean	3.14	2.33	2.86	2.68	2.75	
Comments/Remarks	Good (mean)\geq2.75 to $<$3.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

6.8 Publication Facilities

Table-9: shows the aggregate mean scores on publication facilities is 1.48. That shows comparatively below the average remarks of respondents about different aspects of publications. The aggregate mean score is showing that the

HE govt. colleges are very poor in publication of journals, magazines, and bulletins. All these four colleges sometimes publish a yearly college magazine or a note book and a prospectus for first year students. Very few national or international standard journal is published by them.

TABLE-9: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT PUBLICATION FACILITIES

	Respondents' opinions mean	

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	SD
40. College journals by teachers and students	2.15	1.40	1.25	1.25	1.51	0.71
41. Departmental Journals and bulletins	2.65	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.41	0.82
Aggregate Mean	2.40	1.20	1.13	1.13	1.46	
Comments/Remarks	Below Average (mean<1.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

6.9 Primary Health care/ Medical Center services

Table-10 shows the mean scores on health care/ medical services in selected HE govt. colleges with aggregate mean score 1.95. It shows comparatively the average remarks

of respondents about different aspects of health care/ medical services. They have no full medical center for regular treatment and diagnosis. They have only a part time doctor for one or two hour for giving treatment to the students.

TABLE-10: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT PRIMARY HEALTH CARE/ MEDICAL CENTER SERVICES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' opinions mean					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
42. Indoor Health center facility with doctors, health assistant and nurses	2.70	1.60	2.00	2.00	2.08	0.74
43. Outdoor Health center facility with doctors, health assistant and nurses	2.85	1.30	1.75	1.25	1.79	0.85
44. Health care tools like sphygmomanometer, stethoscope, thermometer, glucometer etc.	2.30	2.20	1.50	1.75	1.94	0.70
45. Free Diagnosis and medicine facilities	2.25	1.50	2.00	2.25	2.00	0.68
Aggregate Mean	2.53	1.65	1.81	1.81	1.95	
Comments/Remarks	Average (Mean>=1.75 to <2.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

6.10 Library facilities

Table-11 shows the mean scores on different facilities of library in selected HE govt. colleges with aggregate mean scores of 2.12. The result shows the 'average' remarks of respondents about different aspects of central library, departmental seminar libraries, and number of books, journals,

periodicals and newspapers. In this regard, RC shows the higher scores of 2.36 with 'average' remarks and DGC shows the lower scores of 1.85 with 'average' remarks. The mean score also shows there is no e-library systems in all the selected govt. colleges.

TABLE-11: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT LIBRARY FACILITIES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' opinions mean					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
46. Central library	3.30	2.80	3.25	3.25	3.15	0.70
47. Departmental Seminar Libraries	2.80	2.70	3.25	3.00	2.94	0.83
48. Book Issuing, printing and photocopy facilities from central and departmental libraries	2.85	2.90	1.75	1.25	2.19	0.99
49. Sufficient No. of Books Journals and Periodicals and Newspapers in library	2.85	2.40	2.25	1.75	2.31	0.80
50. E-library with access of e-books, journals and articles	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Aggregate Mean	2.36	2.16	2.10	1.85	2.12	
Comments/Remarks	Average (Mean>>=1.75 to <2.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19.

6.11 Practical/Laboratory Services

Table-12 shows the mean scores on practical laboratory services in selected HE govt. colleges with aggregate mean scores of 2.81. That shows near 'good' remarks of respondents

about different aspects of practical labs and computer labs facilities. The RC, CCR and DGC have rich laboratories for students of science faculty and computer labs for students as they are some of the oldest colleges in Bangladesh.

TABLE-12: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT PRACTICAL/ LABORATORY SERVICES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' opinions mean					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
51. Physics, Chemistry, Zoology, Botany , Geography, Psychology, Math, and Statistics labs	3.25	2.30	3.00	2.75	2.83	0.41
52. Computers labs	3.25	2.60	3.00	2.25	2.78	0.44
Aggregate Mean	3.25	2.45	3.00	2.50	2.81	
Comments/Remarks	Good (mean>=2.75 to <3.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19.

6.12 Creating Job Opportunities

Table-13 shows the mean scores of 1.15 on creating job opportunities. The result shows the 'below average' remarks of respondents about different aspects of seminars on local and national level, and private and public companies and

delegates, and arrangement of job fairs. The RGWC, CCR and DGC have no arrangement of job fairs and very less arrangement of workshops, seminar and symposium with local and national level private and public companies and delegates.

TABLE-13: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT CREATING JOB OPPORTUNITIES

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' opinions mean					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
53. Arrangement of workshops, seminar and symposium with local and national level private and public companies and delegates	2.40	1.20	2.00	1.25	1.71	0.61
54. Arrangement of Job Fairs	2.35	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.59	1.28
Aggregate Mean	2.38	0.60	1.00	0.63	1.15	
Comments/Remarks	Below Average (mean<1.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

6.13 Awards and recognition for Academic Achievement

Table-6.13 shows the aggregate mean scores on awards and recognition for academic achievement in selected HE govt. colleges. It shows with aggregate mean scores of 2.64 with the 'average' remarks of respondents about different aspects of

achievement and recognitions, prizes and gifts, motivation for creativity and annual sports prize giving ceremony. The study shows 'good' remarks on annual prize giving ceremony but 'average' remarks in other cases.

TABLE-14: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT AWARDS AND RECOGNITION FOR ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' mean opinions					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	

55. Department and college level merit results/achievement recognitions, prizes and gifts	3.20	2.60	2.00	2.75	2.64	0.72
56. Motivating them for new invention	2.80	2.40	2.00	2.00	2.30	0.79
57. Annual Sports prize giving ceremony	3.20	3.50	3.00	2.00	2.93	0.82
Aggregate Mean	3.07	2.83	2.33	2.25	2.64	
Comments/Remarks	Average (Mean)\geq1.75 to $<$2.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

6.14 Other Services Related to Teachers, Students and Staffs

Table-6.14 shows the mean scores on arranging seminars with affiliation university NU and Education Ministry and students regarding exam, evaluation, admission and other issues in selected HE govt. colleges. It shows the aggregate mean scores of 1.99. The Table also shows below the average scores

on different services and facilities to teachers and staffs. The aggregate mean score on different services to others are 2.00. Scores '0.00' shows that the services items are not present in the respective colleges. The CCR and DGC have no 'Power Generator/Solar Panel for self-electricity supply' and RGWC has no Staffs' and Teachers' Quarter and Principal's Residence' to live in.

TABLE-6.14: RESPONDENTS' OPINIONS ABOUT. OTHER SERVICES RELATED TO TEACHERS, STUDENTS AND STAFFS

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation/Number of respondents	Respondents' mean opinions					SD
	RC (20)	RGWC (20)	CCR (20)	DGC (20)	Aggregate mean	
58. Your College arranges seminars with affiliation university NU and education ministry with students regarding exam, evaluation, admission and other issues.	2.75	1.00	1.75	1.00	1.63	0.88
59. Teachers' Lounge	2.80	2.90	2.75	2.50	2.74	0.67
60. Power Generator/Solar Panel for self-electricity supply	2.55	1.60	0.00	0.00	1.04	1.16
61. Services for Teacher and Employees Salary and Honorariums	2.70	2.60	3.00	3.00	2.83	0.59
62. Staffs' and Teachers' Quarter	2.15	0.00	1.75	1.25	1.29	1.00
63. Principal's Residence	3.50	0.00	3.00	3.25	2.44	1.50
Aggregate Mean	2.71	1.35	2.04	1.83	1.99	
Comments/Remarks	Average (Mean)\geq1.75 to $<$2.75)					

Source: Survey Data, 2018-19

7. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Identifying services and their status and quality of HE in govt. colleges is very much important to find out overall service quality. Besides, enrolling the HE students, the govt. colleges are to provide a lot of services and facilities to the students. Every year a lot of HE students are enrolled in these colleges. From the data analysis and discussion we have found that among the 14 services dimensions 9 have 'average' status, 2 has 'below average' and only 3 have 'good' status in terms of their degree of feasibility, availability, accessibility and quality of the services. Among the 63 investigated items/ parameters 41 items have found 'average or below average' remarks and only 22 items have found 'good' remarks of respondents that is poor status of HE in selected govt. colleges.

Quality services are important for quality HE. Govt. colleges are traditional in providing services to the HE students. They have very poor capacity for providing quality services. Govt. colleges get lower allocation of budgets from Govt. than that of the public universities. Budgets are allocated according to the largeness and oldness as well as volume of teachers and staffs of colleges. Therefore, they cannot expand services according to the demand of students equally and cannot maintain status equally. The ratios of different service attributes to the number of students is large. Because of having limited capacity they cannot provide quality services to the large number of stakeholders. It seems that they are only issuing certificates without adopting students to the world of knowledge and to fit them as human resources.

8. CONCLUSION

Education is the sources of all power in the present world. To give quality HE to our young people to make them valuable resources and as human capital, quality services should be ensured. Generally it has been seen that govt. colleges are not in good position for providing HE. Though Govt. colleges are doing better in some aspects, most of the service attributes are of average or below the average status.

The number of students is very large than their capacity. There are some major problems relating to area of lands, number of academic buildings and classrooms, number of teachers, number of students admitted every years. There is a great opportunity for expansion of HE in many govt. colleges in terms of land and natural environmental resources than many other public or private universities. These cannot be effective for lack of quality services. Therefore our Govt. should take steps properly in both national strategies and education policy, and give attention properly to ensure quality HE in Govt. colleges.

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APPENDICES

Appendix-I

Institute of Bangladesh Studies (IBS)

University of Rajshahi (RU)

(Questionnaire for Officers, Teachers and Employees)

[The Data regarding to explore the quality status of existing services for higher education of selected govt. colleges in Bangladesh. In case of any service availability indicating “Yes” or “No” and if a Service is available comparatively denote any of the characteristics of “Very good” or “Good” or “Average” or “Below Average” for degree of availability, accessibility and status or quality of the service item. You are requested to put tick (✓) mark on your opinion in corresponding services items]

Respondent’s Profile:

1. Name of the respondent:

.....

2. Name of College:

.....

3. Status of Respondent: Officer/Teacher/ Employee/,
Designation:

4. Gender: Male/Female

Part-1: To Explore/identify existing services and their status or quality of selected Government colleges affiliated to NU in case of HE.

Service items/ Aspects of Evaluation	Yes=Y No=N	Very good=4 Good=3 Average=2 Below Average=1				
1. Teaching-learning services						
1. Traditional teaching tools/materials: blackboards and chalks, board cleaners/dusters, moving boards etc.	Y	N	4	3	2	1
2. Modern tools and materials: white board and markers, Multimedia Projectors, Sound systems, project pointer, cordless speakers, laptops, pen drives etc.	Y	N	4	3	2	1
3. Class room Physical Environment: Chair bench decoration and Lighting	Y	N	4	3	2	1
4. Class time/schedule and with sufficient class durations	Y	N	4	3	2	1
5. Lesson Plan (lectures time, feedback time, test time, FAQ for students) and Course Plan	Y	N	4	3	2	1
6. Team works for solving study problems	Y	N	4	3	2	1
7. Individual Assignment/group assignments	Y	N	4	3	2	1

8. Course Evaluation (in course/annual test)	Y	N	4	3	2	1
9. Attendances, appearing in the class tests,	Y	N	4	3	2	1
10. Individual and group Presentations of Term Papers, Seminar Papers;	Y	N	4	3	2	1
2. ICT services						
11. Computer lab with using facilities	Y	N	4	3	2	1
12. ICT skill development short courses (MS-Office, internet browsing, email sending, download and upload of files and text etc.)	Y	N	4	3	2	1
13. Broad band/wifi internet using facilities	Y	N	4	3	2	1
3. Administrative services are accessible for students, staffs, teachers and guardians						
14. Sufficient employees for different services	Y	N	4	3	2	1
15. Is there Sufficient Cashiers	Y	N	4	3	2	1
16. Is there sufficient key Information officers	Y	N	4	3	2	1
4. Class room and college environment						
17. Well-equipped and comfortable desks for note taking in the class rooms	Y	N	4	3	2	1
18. Easy accessible toilets and washrooms for both gender disabled-abled students	Y	N	4	3	2	1
19. Comfortable Desk arrangement for group work and group discussions	Y	N	4	3	2	1
20. Well decorated outdoor seats and tents for group discussions	Y	N	4	3	2	1
21. College Buildings and infrastructures are well decorated	Y	N	4	3	2	1
22. College trees’ gardens and flowers’ gardens are well decorated and, neat and clean	Y	N	4	3	2	1
5. Co-curricular and extracurricular activities (Attach a List)						
23. Sufficient BNCC and rover scout volunteers from different sessions and departments	Y	N	4	3	2	1
24. Multi-functional clubs to enhance students’ personal development and creativity	Y	N	4	3	2	1
25. Facilities in different co-curricular and extracurricular activities	Y	N	4	3	2	1
26. Arrangement of different types of fairs (science fair, Olympiads etc.)	Y	N	4	3	2	1
6. Accommodation Facilities:						
27. In hostel accommodation with neat and clean environment	Y	N	4	3	2	1
28. Outside hostel accommodation, Good mess, hostels etc. nearer to college	Y	N	4	3	2	1
29. Comfortable beddings in hostel seats boarding facilities	Y	N	4	3	2	1

30. Indoor and outdoor game and sports and football and cricket tournaments in hostels	Y	N	4	3	2	1
31. Well decorated Guest room to meet students with guardians	Y	N	4	3	2	1
32. Common rooms for ladies and gents	Y	N	4	3	2	1
7. Recreation Facilities						
33. Central auditorium for arranging meetings, occasions, seminar and symposiums etc	Y	N	4	3	2	1
34. Central religious institutions for prayer	Y	N	4	3	2	1
35. Central gymnasium with tools and equipment with a skilled physician	Y	N	4	3	2	1
36. Games and Sports tournaments with different years	Y	N	4	3	2	1
37. Arrangement of national days and cultural functions	Y	N	4	3	2	1
38. Study tours/Excursion every year	Y	N	4	3	2	1
39. TV rooms with satellite channel connections	Y	N	4	3	2	1
8. Facilities for publication						
40. College journals by teachers and students	Y	N	4	3	2	1
41. Departmental Journals and bulletins	Y	N	4	3	2	1
9. Primary Health care/ Medical service services						
42. Indoor Health center facility with doctors, health assistant and nurses	Y	N	4	3	2	1
43. Outdoor Health center facility with doctors, health assistant and nurses	Y	N	4	3	2	1
44. Health care tools like sphygmomanometer, stethoscope, thermometer, glucometer etc.	Y	N	4	3	2	1
45. Free Diagnosis and medicine facilities	Y	N	4	3	2	1
10. Library Services						
46. Central library	Y	N	4	3	2	1
47. Departmental Seminar Libraries	Y	N	4	3	2	1
48. Book Issuing, printing and photocopy facilities from central and departmental libraries	Y	N	4	3	2	1
49. Sufficient No. of Books Journals and Periodicals and News papers in library	Y	N	4	3	2	1
50. E-library with access of e-books and journals and articles	Y	N	4	3	2	1
11. Practical Laboratory Services						
51. Physics, Chemistry, Zoology, Botany, Geography, Psychology, Math, and Statistics labs	Y	N	4	3	2	1
52. Computers labs	Y	N	4	3	2	1
12. Creating Job opportunities						
53. Arrangement of workshops, seminar and symposium with local and national level private and public companies and delegates	Y	N	4	3	2	1
54. Arrangement of Job Fairs	Y	N	4	3	2	1
13. Awards and recognition for Academic Achievement						

55. Department and college level merit results/achievement recognitions, prizes and gifts	Y	N	4	3	2	1
56. Motivating them for new invention	Y	N	4	3	2	1
57. Annual Sports prize giving ceremony	Y	N	4	3	2	1
14. Other Services to teachers, staffs and students						
58. Your College arranges seminars with affiliation university NU and education ministry with students regarding exam, evaluation, admission and other issues.	Y	N	4	3	2	1
59. Teachers' Lounge	Y	N	4	3	2	1
60. Power Generator/Solar Panel for own electricity supply	Y	N	4	3	2	1
61. Services for Teacher and Employees Salary	Y	N	4	3	2	1
62. Staffs' and Teachers' Quarter	Y	N	4	3	2	1
63. Principal's Residence	Y	N	4	3	2	1

Signature of respondents

Thanks a lot for your kind cooperation

Appendix-II

Institute of Bangladesh Studies (IBS)

University of Rajshahi (RU)

Check list for Staff

1. Name of Respondent:

2. Name of College:

2. Status of Respondent: Officer/ Teacher/ Employee/ Student

General Data of Selected Government Colleges

Sl. No.	Items	Information
1.	Name of College	
1.	Year of Establishment	
2.	Area of Land (acre)	
3.	Name of Faculty	
4.	Degree awarded	
5.	No. of Total Departments	
6.	Name of Honours Subjects	
7.	Name of Masters Subjects	
8.	Name of Previous Masters Subjects	
9.	Physics Lab	
10.	Chemistry Lab	
1	Zoology lab	
1.	Botany Lab	
2.		
1	Math Lab	
3.		

1	Statistics Lab	
4.		
1	Psychology Lab	
5.		
1	Geography Lab	
6.		
1	No. of teachers (acting)	
7.		
1	No. Demonstrators	
8.		
1	Physical teacher	
9.		
2	Librarian and Assistant Librarian	
0.		
2	No. of employees regular	
1.		
2	No. of employees master roll	
2.		
2	No. of students studying	
3.		
2	No. Academic Building	
4.		
2	No. of hostels with boarding capacity	
5.		
2	Auditorium	
6.		
2	Central mosque	
7.		
2	Vehicle parking (Car, Cycle -Motor cycle garage for students)	
8.		
2	Teachers' Quarters	
9.		
3	Principal Quarter	
0.		
3	Guest Houses	
1.		
3	Teachers' lounge	
2.		
3	Female students Common room	
3.		
3	Male students common room	
4.		
3	Shohid Minar	
5.		
3	Botanical Garden	
6.		
3	Garden of rare plants and trees	
7.		
3	Zoo Diversity pond	
8.		
3	College magazine	
9.		
4	No. of published national Journal	
0.		
4	No. of published International Journal	
1.		

4	Drinking water in Populous places	
2.		
4	Travelling Libraries in college campus	
3.		
4	Play ground	
4.		
4	BNCC Building	
5.		
4	No. of Computer labs	
6.		
4	No. of General Class rooms	
7.		
4	No. of Multimedia Class rooms	
8.		
4	No. of capacity seat for exam	
9.		
5	Internet connection with Broad Band (Own lease server LAN, Broad band and wifi)	
0.		
5	Degree offered (Degree pass/ Hons/previous/master final/all)	
1		
5	Administrative Building	
2.		
5	Academic Building	
3.		
5	Central Library	
4.		
5	Total No. of Books in central library	
5.		
5	No. of Reference books	
6.		
5	No. of academic books	
7.		
5	Seminar Libraries (Departmental)	
8.		
5	Exam Control room	
9.		
6	Conference room	
0.		
6	Students Parliament	
1.		
6	Reporters Unity	
2.		
6	Museum	
3.		
6	Health center	
4.		
6	Banking transaction booth/Bank	
5.		
6	Mobile banking service for students payments	
6.		
6	Canteen and snacks service	
7.		
6	Postal service (Sub/Full)	
8.		

6 9.	College Transportation service for students no. of Buses	
7 0.	69.1 No. of Seats in buses	
7 1.	69.2 Times travel daily	
7 2.	No. of Departments for Honours course (List)	
7 3.	No. of Departments for Masters course (List)	
7 4.	No. of Co-curricular activities org. (name list)	
7 5.	No. of extra-curricular activities (name list)	
7 6.	No. Cultural Org. (name list)	
7 7.	Rover Den (No. of Members and activities)	
7 8.	BNCC (No. of Members and activities)	
7 9.	Bandhon ((No. of Members and activities)	
8 0.	Girls ranger Guide (No. of Members and activities)	
8 1.	Gymnasium (Tools and No. of regular member)	

Signature

Thanks a lot for your kind cooperation

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